

Spectrophotometric determination of bromhexine using 1,2-naphthoquinone -4-sulfonate (NQS) reagent in bulk and tablet

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ABSTRACT

The primary aim of the current research is to establish a cost-effective spectrophotometric technique for the precise quantification of bromhexine by utilizing NQS as a reagent. The advantage of using NQS is its cost-effectiveness. In the concentration range spanning from 20 to 100 µg/mL, Beer's law was accurately followed for the determination of bromhexine when employing NQS as the reagent. Notably, the correlation coefficient for bromhexine in this context was found to be 0.999. As per the study's results, the limit of detection for bromhexine using NQS was measured at 0.55 µg/mL, while the limit of quantification stood at 1.36 µg/mL. This recommended analytical method offer a high degree of specificity, sensitivity, and repeatability, making them suitable for the evaluation of bromhexine's quality in both bulk and commercial dosage formulations as part of a quality control assessment.

KEYWORDS

Bromhexine hydrochloride, 1,2-Naphthoquinone-4-sulfonate reagent, Visible spectroscopy, pharmaceutical dosage form.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bromhexine hydrochloride was first developed in the year 1950 in the Boehringer Ingelheim research laboratory, was patented in 1961 and in the year 1961 it was introduced into market under the trade name Bisolvon. It is chemically 2-amino-N-cyclohexyl-3,5 dibromo-N-methylbenzylamine hydrochloride most commonly used as mucolytic [1,2] to decrease the viscosity of the sputum so that it can be readily expelled from the respiratory tract. It acts by increasing the bronchial secretions. A study was conducted and proved that bromhexine hydrochloride used in prophylactic treatment in decreasing the rate of SARS-COV-2

infections[3–5] among the healthcare workers. There are many reported spectrophotometric methods for estimation of bromhexine independently [6–10] or in combination with other drugs [11,12]. Various HPLC [13–17], HPTLC [18] and hyphenated methods [19] were also developed individually and in combination with other drugs. Apart from the above methods there are LC-MS, gas liquid chromatography and ion pair HPLC methods, capillary electrophoresis and chemiluminescence methods that were developed for estimation of bromhexine. From the extensive literature study, it was observed that there are no spectrophotometric methods reported with NQS as chromogenic reagent. The method developed was simple, accurate, with no extensive extraction methods and was cost-effective.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1.1. Materials

Bromhexine Hydrochloride was procured from Aurobindo Laboratories Limited, Hyderabad as gift sample. Bromhexine EG was purchased from Apollo Pharmacy, Hyderabad. Methanol, NQS reagent and potassium hydroxide all were of analytical grade and were procured from Oxford Lab Fine Chem LLP, Mumbai. Analytical balance of Shimadzu AUX 220 model, UV-Visible Spectrophotometer of Shimadzu UV-1800 model, Japan and melting point apparatus of Bio-Tech, Mumbai were utilized in the current analysis.

2.1.2. Drug Authentication Studies

Drug authentication was carried out determining melting point, by performing solubility studies and by detring the λ_{\max} using the UV Spectrophotometer.

2.1.3. Preparation of standard stock solution

A precise measurement of 10 mg of Bromhexine hydrochloride was carefully weighed and subsequently transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask. The substance was dissolved in methanol, and the solution's volume was adjusted to the flask's mark by adding methanol.

2.1.4. Preparation of 0.5 % NQS reagent

The reagent 1,2-Naphthoquinone-4-sulfonate (NQS) of 0.5gms was dissolved in a small volume of water and then brought up to a final volume of 100 mL using distilled water.

2.1.5. Preparation of 2% potassium hydroxide (KOH) Solution:

Potassium hydroxide pellets 2 gm was dissolved in few ml of water and made up to 100 ml with distilled water.

2.2. Analytical Method Development

2.2.1. Method optimization

2.2.1.1. Selection of solvents

The stock (1000 µg/ml) of bromhexine was prepared using methanol and dilutions were made using methanol.

2.2.1.2. Effect of concentration of NQS reagent

The impact of varying chromogenic reagent concentrations (0.2 %, 0.3 %, 0.4 %, 0.5 %, 0.6 %) on absorbance was assessed, and the corresponding data is presented in the results and discussions section.

2.2.1.3. Effect of concentration of potassium hydroxide

The influence of chromogenic reagent concentration was investigated using a range of concentrations (0 %, 1 %, 1.5 %, 2 %, 2.5 %, 3 %), and absorbance measurements were conducted. The resulting data is detailed in the results and discussions section.

2.2.1.4. Effect of reaction time on chromogenic reagent

The impact of reaction duration on the chromogenic reagent was examined at different time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 minutes), with absorbance measurements recorded at each interval. The gathered data is presented in the results and discussions section.

2.2.1.5. Selection of suitable wave length:

A 10 µg/mL drug solution was prepared by mixing 1 mL of the standard stock solution with 1 mL of 0.5 % NQS solution, 1 mL of 2 % KOH, and then diluting to the mark with methanol. Subsequently, a spectral analysis in the visible range (400-800 nm) was conducted, and the resulting spectrum is presented in the results section.

2.2.1.6. Procedure for Calibration curve:

Standard solutions of Bromhexine Hydrochloride (0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1 mL) were individually transferred into a series of 10 mL volumetric flasks. In each flask, 1 mL of 0.5 % NQS reagent and 1 mL of 2 % w/v potassium hydroxide were added. After allowing the mixtures to stand for 5 minutes, the solutions were brought up to their respective marks with methanol and left undisturbed for an additional 15 minutes to facilitate the reaction. The absorbance of the resulting orange-colored chromogen for Bromhexine was measured at 457 nm, with a reagent blank serving as the reference. Linearity was assessed across concentration ranges of approximately 20-100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Subsequently, the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and the correlation coefficient of the standard curves ($n=3$) were calculated.

2.3. Analytical Method Validation:

The procedure validation adhered to the guidelines set by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), involving an evaluation of the following vital attributes:

Linearity, accuracy, precision, Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

2.3.1. Linearity

Linearity was assessed employing the least squares regression method. In this context, Linearity refers to the capacity of an analytical method in order to generate test results that demonstrate a direct proportionality to the concentration of the analyte in the samples, either through a direct relationship or well-defined mathematical transformations. The calibration curve demonstrated linearity across a concentration range of about 20-100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Regression analysis provided an equation that described this relationship. Parameters including the correlation coefficient, the mean \pm standard deviation (SD), slope, intercept, and correlation coefficient of the standard curve were computed using triplicate measurements ($n=3$).

2.3.2. Precision

The precision of the method was determined through both intra-day and inter-day variation studies. Repeatability assessments were performed to assess the precision of the method within a single day (intra-day) and across multiple days (inter-day).

For these studies, three distinct concentrations (20, 60, 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were employed. In the intra-day studies, the analysis of these concentrations was repeated three times within a single day. In the inter-day variation studies, the analysis of the same concentrations was repeated

on three separate days within the same laboratory. The precision results are represented as the percentage Relative Standard Deviation (%RSD).

2.3.3. Accuracy

The accuracy of the method was assessed through a series of recovery experiments. In these experiments, reference standards of the drug were added to the formulation at three specific levels: 80 %, 100 %, and 120 % of the expected concentration. These recovery studies were conducted on three distinct occasions to ensure their strength and dependability. The method's accuracy was confirmed through these recovery experiments, and it was determined to meet acceptable specification limits. The outcomes were reported as percentage recovery, and the percentage relative standard deviations for Bromhexine's recovery were computed

2.3.4. Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification

The assessment of the Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) for the procedure followed ICH guidelines and entailed samples with exceedingly low analyte concentrations. These values were computed using the following formulas, based on the linearity data: The equations for the Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) are as follows:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times (\sigma / S)$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times (\sigma / S)$$

Where:

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve of the analyte

These calculations contribute to defining the analytical method's sensitivity and its ability to detect analytes at low concentrations.

2.4. ASSAY OF BROMHEXINE IN TABLET DOSAGE FORM

Ten tablets, each containing 8 mg of Bromhexine, underwent precise weighing to determine their average weight. The tablets were disassembled, and the powder obtained was weighed to find its average weight. A quantity corresponding to 10 mg of the active ingredient was dissolved in methanol, and the volume was adjusted to 10 mL with methanol, yielding the creation of a stock solution. The stock solution was filtered by passing it through Whatman filter paper. From the filtered solution, 1 mL was extracted and mixed with methanol to create a standard solution with a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. In a 10 mL volumetric flask, 1 mL of the standard solution was combined with 1 mL of 0.5 % w/v NQS and 1 mL of 2 % KOH.

The flask was filled to the mark with methanol and allowed to stand for 15 minutes. The absorbance of the resulting orange-coloured chromogen was measured at a specific wavelength and compared to a reagent blank. The drug content was assessed, and the results were subjected to validation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Drug Authentication Studies

3.1.1. Melting point:

The Bromhexine melting point was ascertained through the capillary tube method, and the findings confirmed that the Bromhexine melting point was consistent with the expected range specified. The M.P are represented in the Table (1).

Table 1. Melting point of Bromhexine

Drug Name	Melting Point
Reference M. P	232 ±3°C
Measured M. P	231 -235°C

3.1.2. Solubility studies:

The solubility of Bromhexine was assessed by dissolving the drug in various solvents, including methanol, ethanol, water, and DMSO. Among these solvents, methanol demonstrated excellent solubility for the drug. Consequently, methanol was chosen as the preferred solvent for further use and the solubility profile of the drug in various solvents are represented in the Table (2).

Table 2. Solubility of Bromhexine

Solvent	Solubility
Methanol	Highly soluble
Ethanol	Sparingly soluble
Water	Poorly soluble
DMSO	Slightly soluble

3.1.3. Determination of λ_{\max} :

The Bromhexine drug was scanned between 400-200 nm and λ_{\max} (Fig.1) was found to be 317 nm.

Fig. (1). UV Spectrum of Bromhexine (10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) in methanol

3.2. Analytical Method Development

3.2.1. Method optimization

3.2.1.1. Effect of KOH concentration

The effect of KOH concentration (Fig.2) was determined by taking concentrations (0.5 %,1 %, 1.5 %, 2 %, 2,5 %, 3 %) and at 2 % w/v of KOH maximum absorbance was observed. So, 2% concentration of KOH was selected for bromhexine determination.

Fig. (2). Effect of KOH concentration

3.2.1.2.Effect of concentration of NQS

The impact of varying chromogenic reagent concentrations (Fig.3) was investigated by testing different concentrations (0.2 %, 0.3 %, 0.4 %, 0.5 %, 0.6 %). It was noted that the highest absorbance was achieved with NQS reagent at a concentration of 0.5 % w/v. Consequently, the 0.5 % NQS reagent concentration was selected as the ideal choice for Bromhexine determination.

Fig. (3). Effect of concentration of NQS

3.2.1.3. Effect of reaction time on chromogenic reagent

The influence of reaction time on the chromogenic reagent (Fig.4) was investigated at various time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 minutes). It was noted that the peak absorbance was attained at the 15-minute interval, and this maximum absorbance remained constant for up to 25 minutes.

Fig. (4). Effect of reaction time on chromogenic reagent

3.2.1.4. Principle

The suggested spectrophotometric method relies on the interaction between NQS and Bromhexine in the presence of potassium hydroxide (KOH). The sodium sulfonate group in NQS is replaced with the aromatic amine group when NQS treated with primary or secondary amine containing compound. The orange-coloured chromogen (Fig.5) absorbance is measured at visible wavelength at 457 nm.

Fig. (5). Reaction mechanism of Bromhexine with NQS reagent

3.2.1.5. Selection of suitable wavelength

The Bromhexine standard solution was scanned under UV-visible range between (400 to 800 nm) and spectra obtained was shown in figure. From the spectra (Fig.6) suitable wavelength for the drug (Bromhexine) was found to be at 457 nm.

Fig. (6). UV - Visible spectrum of Bromhexine (10µg/mL)

3.3. ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION

3.3.1. Linearity studies

Linearity was assessed through the least squares regression method, confirming that Bromhexine exhibited linearity (Fig.7) over the concentration range of around 20-100 µg/mL. The calibration curve in this examined range exhibited a linear relationship, with the regression analysis equation represented as $y = 0.0147x + 0.012$. The correlation coefficient (R^2) was computed (Fig.8) and yielded a value of 0.999. Furthermore, the mean \pm standard deviation (SD), slope, intercept, and correlation coefficient of the standard curve were determined from three replicates ($n=3$). The data for these calculations are provided below.

Table. 3 Linearity Data of Bromhexine Hydrochloride

Concentration($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance ($\text{AM}\pm\text{SD}$) (n=3)
20	0.3069 \pm 0.0358
40	0.5561 \pm 0.0311
60	0.7697 \pm 0.0176
80	0.8427 \pm 0.0851
100	1.0534 \pm 0.1801

Fig. (7). Linearity spectrum of Bromhexine (20-100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)

Fig. (8) Calibration plot of Bromhexine

3.3.2. Precision

Intermediate precision was evaluated by performing inter-day analysis (n=3) on three standard solutions of Bromhexine, each with concentrations of 20, 60, and 100 µg/mL. Simultaneously, the method's repeatability, representing intra-day precision, was established through intra-day analysis (n=3) of three standard solutions of Bromhexine, all with concentrations of 20, 60, and 100 µg/mL. The data acquired from these precision studies is presented in a table. The % RSD (Relative Standard Deviation) values for both intra-day and inter-day assessments consistently remained below 2.0 %. This outcome highlights the method's exceptional precision and reliability.

Concentration (µg/mL)	Intra-day precision		Inter-day precision	
	Concentration Estimated(µg/mL) AM±SD (n=3)	% RSD	Concentration estimated (µg/mL) AM±SD (n=3)	% RSD
20	19.1±0.05	0.261	19.2±0.1	0.520
60	58.5±0.432	0.738	58.4±0.471	0.806
100	98.3±1.01	1.027	98.2±1.11	1.130

Table.4 Precision data of Bromhexine

3.3.3. Accuracy

The method's accuracy was confirmed through recovery studies, and it was ascertained to be well within the specified limits. The results revealed a % recovery ranging from 99 %

Brand Name	Recovery level (%)	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount Of drug spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Total amount of drug($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount of drug found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) AM \pm SD (n=3)	% recovery	RSD (%)
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to 101 %, signifying the method's ability to accurately retrieve the expected values for the drug. Furthermore, the % RSD (Relative Standard Deviation) consistently stayed below 2 %, emphasizing the precision and consistent performance of the method. The comprehensive results of these accuracy and precision evaluations are provided in a table summarizing the method's performance

Table .5 Data for accuracy of Bromhexine Hydrochloride

Bromhexine	80	40	32	72	71.33±0.098	97.98	0.53
Hydrochloride	100	40	40	80	80.59±0.0109	99.06	0.55
(8mg)	120	40	48	88	88.07±0.0124	99.7	0.57

3.3.4. Limit of detection (LOD), Limit of quantification (LOQ)

The Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) for bromhexine were determined, and the corresponding values have been documented in the table.

Table .6 Data for LOD and LOQ

Bromhexine Hydrochloride	Limit of detection	0.55 µg/mL
	Limit of quantification	1.66 µg/mL

3.4. Assay of Bromhexine in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

The assay results fell within the range of 90-101 %, which is equivalent to the specified range of 90-102 %. The detailed assay results are presented in a table. This suggests that the method provided precise and dependable measurements well within the acceptable range for the assay.

Table .7 Data for assay studies

Formulation	Label claim (mg)	Amount found AM±SD (n=3)	% Assay	% RSD
Bromhexine 8mg	8	7.933±0.081	99.1	1.021

3.5. System Suitability:

The optimized overall characteristics for bromhexine were reported in table.

Table .8 System suitability parameters for Bromhexine

Parameters	Value
Absorption wavelength (nm)	457
Linearity range (20-100 µg/mL)	20-100
Limit of Detection (nm)	0.55
Limit of Quantification (nm)	1.36
Molar absorptivity (L. mol/cm)	2.429
Sandell sensitivity (µg/mL)	0.01698
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.999
Slope (m)	0.12
Intercept (c)	0.0147
Regression equation (y)	$Y=0.12X+0.0147$

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, we have successfully developed a straightforward, specific, and cost-effective spectrophotometric method that employs the chromogenic reagent NQS (1,2 Naphthoquinone-4-sulfonate). The proposed method offers simplicity, sensitivity, and accuracy for spectrophotometric quantification of Bromhexine in tablet dosage forms. The % assay value obtained from the marketed formulation was 99.1%, indicating strong agreement with the label claim and affirming the method's scientific soundness, free from interference. The method demonstrated enhanced sensitivity compared to existing methods, with calculated Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) values of 0.55 and 1.66 µg/mL, respectively. The approach is not only cost-effective but also minimizes the need for extensive extraction steps and conserves solvent use, offering distinct advantages over alternative techniques. The developed method saves time and obviates the necessity for

intricate chromatographic procedures. Considering these characteristics, the proposed method is particularly well-suited for routine analysis in quality control laboratories, especially for the assessment of Bromhexine in tablet dosage forms.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

FUNDING

None

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

Not applicable.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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